

Statistical Evaluation of Lightpath Feasibility in Converged Optical Metro-Access Networks

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Abstract—This paper analyzes the feasible Bit Error Rate (BER) for all lightpaths in a converged metro-access network. By modeling physical impairments across segments, it builds a statistical BER profile, enabling evaluation of signal integrity and lightpath feasibility under diverse network conditions.

Index Terms—metro-access optical networks, BER analysis

I. INTRODUCTION

With the growing demand for faster, more efficient communication networks driven by technologies like 5G, IoT, and cloud services, managing resources in both wireless and optical systems has become a critical challenge. The evolution of mobile networks from 5G towards 6G and the large volume of data traffic associated with these advancements highlight the inadequacy of traditional wireless networks for fronthauling, primarily due to their limited bandwidth. It necessitates substantial enhancements in per-antenna capacity and reliable connectivity solutions to support dramatically increased data rates, ultra-low latency, and higher reliability [1]

In metropolitan areas, where the demographic push is driving the rapid deployment of numerous antennas, these antennas are invariably connected to virtualized Baseband Units (BBUs). This connection demands high capacity in terms of bandwidth and bitrate. Several transport technologies have been proposed to support such applications using optical fiber and wireless technologies such as microwave and millimeter (mm) waves, terahertz (THz), and free-space optics [2, 3]. Each of these has its own advantages and disadvantages, but optical fiber has been regarded as the most effective transport technology for fronthauling and backhauling because it offers high bandwidth, reliable and low latency communication with minimal signal losses for supporting 5G and future 6G applications [1, 4].

Dedicated fibers can be used for such purposes, but typically they aren't scalable or cost-effective, especially in dense urban environments with dynamic and heterogeneous traffic patterns. An alternative approach is to use the existing optical infras-

tructure for supporting access networks, offering a unique opportunity in this context. This infrastructure typically includes a metropolitan area network carrying classical Dense Wavelength Division Multiplexing channels (DWDM) channels, whereas the access segment carries a Passive Optical Network (PON) forming the backbone of urban fiber infrastructure. In this scenario, reliable transmission over these shared and often suboptimally utilized resources, it becomes critical to evaluate the feasibility of each potential lightpath from a physical-layer perspective. In this study, we investigate the statistical evaluation of Bit Error Rate (BER) across all feasible lightpaths in a converged metro-access network, depicted in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Conceptual architecture of Converged Metro-Access optical Network

II. SIMULATION SCENARIO

To evaluate the physical layer characteristics for all possible lightpaths in a converged metro-access network, the overall network has been modeled in the Python framework. In this study, we have considered the metro-access network topology depicted in Fig. 2 with a limited subset of available leaves, exchanging antenna-to-antenna traffic. It consists of 37 optical nodes for a converged metro-access network for add-drop traffic requests. The M-nodes are representing metro network while A-nodes are representing access segment. Metro nodes

are interconnected by 19 edges representing optical line systems, each consisting of fiber pairs and in-line amplifiers. The network features an average node degree of 3.42, an average link length of 37 km, with a maximum link length of 50 km. Access network segments are connected to metro network via five edge links. The access segment consists of short-reach fiber links ranging from 2 km to 5 km. This access segment is based on the passive optical network (PON) configurations, having an average splitting ratio of 1:4.

The physical-layer modeling accounts for key impairments such as fiber attenuation and amplifier noise introduced by optical line systems. For each lightpath, the cumulative effect of these impairments is used to compute metrics such as the received optical power (ROP), generalized signal-to-noise ratio (GSNR), and end-to-end signal-to-noise ratio (SNR).

To determine the feasibility of each lightpath on the converged metro-access network, we have considered random power loss distribution on the access segment as illustrated in [5]. Considering a transceiver model as in [6], the bit error rate (BER) for each lightpath has been computed using eq. 1 for which SNR contribution is given by eq. 2.

$$\text{BER} = k_1 \cdot \text{erfc} \left(\sqrt{k_2 \cdot \text{SNR}} \right) \quad (1)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are constants that depends on the modulation format [7].

$$\text{SNR}^{-1} = \text{GSNR}^{-1} + \text{SNR}_{\text{TRX}}^{-1} \quad (2)$$

Based on the computed BER for each lightpath, the feasibility of the lightpath has been decided by comparing it with BER threshold. It reflects the bitrate and capacity of the network.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

We assessed lightpath feasibility using BER thresholds of 10^{-2} and 10^{-3} for both 200G DP-QPSK and 400G DP-16QAM signals, assuming a Cassini DCO transceiver, 1 THz spectrum, 100 GHz channel spacing, and 64 Gbaud symbol rate. Table I summarizes the percentage of feasible lightpaths under both configurations.

For a high BER threshold of 10^{-3} , DP-QPSK shows higher resilience, resulting 63.11% feasible LPs compared to only 10.02% for DP-16QAM. However, when the BER threshold is considered to be 10^{-2} , the percentage of feasible LPs increases to 85.73% and 52.38% for DP-SPSK and DP-16QAM, respectively. It highlights the impact of modulation format and BER thresholds on the lightpath feasibility, as higher-order modulations like 16-QAM are more sensitive to noise and signal degradation, requiring better-quality paths to meet BER constraints.

Cassini DCO	BER	Modulation Format	Feasible L.P	Non-Feasible L.P
	10^{-3}		DP 16-QAM	408 (10.02%)
		DP-QPSK	2570 (63.11%)	1502 (36.89%)
10^{-2}		DP 16-QAM	2133 (52.38%)	1939 (47.62%)
		DP-QPSK	3491 (85.73%)	581 (14.27%)

TABLE I: BER-based feasibility analysis of Cassini DCO

Despite its lower lightpath feasibility under strict BER constraints, DP-16QAM enables higher data throughput, supporting 400 Gbps per channel compared to 200 Gbps for DP-QPSK. Given the channel spacing of 100 GHz within a 1 THz spectrum, the system accommodates a limited number of high-capacity channels, highlighting the need to optimize both spectral efficiency and error tolerance. DP-16QAM, with higher spectral efficiency, is ideal for high-speed traffic in shorter paths, while DP-QPSK ensures more reliable transmission over longer or more impaired routes. This trade-off between capacity and lightpath feasibility underscores the importance of dynamic modulation adaptation in optical resource management, where modulation formats are intelligently selected based on network conditions, traffic demands, and quality of transmission metrics to maximize overall system performance.

Fig. 2: Converged Metro-Access Network Topology

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